

24-dehydrocholesterol / 3 β -hydroxysterol Δ^{24} reductase (DHCR24) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : Flavoproteins are proteins that contain a nucleic acid derivative of riboflavin and have either FMN (flavin mononucleotide) or FAD (flavin adenine dinucleotide) as a prosthetic group or as a cofactor. DHCR24 encodes a flavin adenine dinucleotide (FAD)-dependent oxidoreductase, which catalyzes the reduction of the Δ^{24} double bond of sterol intermediates during cholesterol biosynthesis. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of DHCR24, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related

^{*}ML dicoveries of DHCR24 synergy in Meningiomas

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to meningiomas.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp

et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angioma-tous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Wurttemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. 24-dehydrocholesterol / 3 β -hydroxysterol Δ^24 reductase (DHCR24)

In Alzheimer's disease (AD) brains, selected populations of neurons degenerate heavily, while others do not degenerate. To explore the cellular basis for this selective vulnerability of neurons in distinct brain regions, Greeve et al. [13] compared gene expression between the severely affected inferior temporal lobes and the mostly unaffected fronto-parietal cortices by using an mRNA differential display. They identified seladin-1 (selective Alzheimer's disease indicator-1 or DHCR24), a novel gene, which was downregulated in large pyramidal neurons in vulnerable regions in AD

but not control brains. Seladin-1/DHCR24 sequence shares similarities with flavin-adenin-dinucleotide (FAD)-dependent oxidoreductases. In - • human control brain, they found seladin-1/DHCR24 to be highly expressed in almost all neurons and • PC12 cell clones that were selected for resistance against AD-associated amyloid- β peptide ($A\beta$)-induced toxicity, they found that both mRNA and protein levels of seladin-1/DHCR24 were approximately 3-fold higher as compared with the non-resistant wild-type cells. Their results established that seladin-1/DHCR24 was an important factor for the protection of cells against $A\beta$ toxicity and oxidative stress, and they suggested that seladin-1/DHCR24 might be involved in the regulation of cell survival and death.

Desmosterolosis is a rare autosomal recessive disorder characterized by multiple congenital anomalies. Desmosterolosis patients have elevated levels of the cholesterol precursor desmosterol, in plasma, tissue, and cultured cells, which points to a deficiency of the enzyme DHCR24. DHCR24 in cholesterol biosynthesis, is known to catalyze the reduction of the Δ^{24} double bond of sterol intermediates. Waterham et al. [14] identified the human DHCR24 cDNA and its heterologous expression in the yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, followed by enzyme-activity measurements, confirmed that it encodes DHCR24. They found that conversion of desmosterol to cholesterol by DHCR24 in vitro was strictly dependent on reduced nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate and increased twofold by the addition of FAD to the assay. Their data showed that desmosterolosis was a cholesterol-biosynthesis disorder caused by mutations in DHCR24.

1.3. Roles of DHCR24 in different disease

Di Stasi et al. [15] isolated DHCR24 as highly expressed in a short-term **melanoma** cell line derived from a cutaneous metastases (S/M2) compared to that obtained from the autologous primary tumor (S/P). Their gene expression analysis confirmed that DHCR24 was 5-fold upregulated in S/M2 compared to S/P cells, with high level expression detected in 13/25 melanoma metastases and in 1/7 primary melanomas (thus indicating its upregulation might occur in melanoma progression). In S/M2 cells, high DHCR24 expression associated with resistance to apoptosis triggered by oxidative stress induced by exposure to hydrogen peroxide. They showed that DHCR24 gene transfer protected melanoma cells from H_2O_2 -induced cytotoxicity.

Seladin-1 being is expressed in the pituitary gland, Luciani et al. [16] determined its expression level in **pituitary tumors**, i.e. GH-secreting and nonfunctioning pituitary adenomas (NFPA), and whether differential expression might be associated with different somatostatin (sst)-induced apoptosis. Their results suggested that differential seladin-1 expression in pituitary adenomas might be associated with a different apoptotic response to sst analogs.

The **cornea** matures after birth to develop a fully functional, refractive and protective barrier tissue. Wu et al. [17] investigated the complex biological events underlying this process by profiling global genome-wide gene expression patterns of the immature postnatal day 10 and seven week-old adult mouse cornea. They further induced the lens and tendon in the study to increase the specificity of genes identified as up regulated in the corneal samples. They observed similarities in gene expression between the cornea and the tendon were in the mesenchymal extracellular matrix collagen (types

I/III/V/VI) and proteoglycan (lumican, decorin and biglycan) genes. They found approximately 76 genes over expressed in the cornea samples that showed basal expression levels in the lens and tendon; 32 of these were novel with no known functions in the cornea, one of which was DHCR24 with a potential role in protection against oxidative stress.

Prostate cancer (CaP) represents a major leading cause of morbidity and mortality in the Western world, with elevated cholesterol levels, resulting from altered cholesterol metabolism, found in CaP cells. Bonaccorsi et al. [18] demonstrated the androgen regulation of seladin-1/DHCR24 expression, due to the presence of androgen responsive element sequences in its promoter region. They found reduced amount of seladin-1/DHCR24 expression and cholesterol, in metastatic androgen receptor-negative CaP cells, compared to androgen receptor-positive cells. In tumor samples from 61 patients who underwent radical prostatectomy the expression of seladin-1/DHCR24 was observed to be higher w.r.t to normal tissues. In a first, they demonstrated that the androgen regulation of the seladin-1/DHCR24 gene and the presence of a higher level of expression in CaP tissues, compared to the normal prostate, thus pointing to an involvement of this gene in CaP.

McGrath et al. [19] investigated the ability of high-density lipoproteins (HDLs) to upregulate genes with the potential to protect against inflammation in endothelial cells. They exposed human coronary artery endothelial cells (HCAECs) to reconstituted HDLs (rHDLs) for 16 hours before being activated with tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) for 5 hours. They observed that rHDLs decreased vascular cell adhesion molecule-1 (VCAM-1) promoter activity via the nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B) binding site. rHDLs suppressed the canonical NF- κ B pathway and decreased many NF- κ B target genes. This suppression of NF- κ B and VCAM-1 expression by rHDLs or native HDLs was dependent on an increase in DHCR24 levels. Their results suggested that **antiinflammatory effects** of rHDLs were mediated partly through an upregulation of DHCR24.

To study the molecular basis for the exquisite sensitivity of **testicular germ cell tumours** of adolescents and adults (TGCTs), i.e seminomas and non-seminomatous germ cell tumours, to chemo/radiotherapy, Nuti et al. [20] assessed the expression of seladin-1 in different histological types of TGCTs, known to have varying treatment sensitivity, in order to establish whether this protein may influence cisplatin responsiveness in vitro. They confirmed their results of using a non-seminomatous cell line model (NT2) before and after differentiation with retinoic acid. They observed significantly higher seladin-1 expression in the differentiated derivatives (teratoma) and found an inverse relationship seladin-1 expression and the amount of cleaved caspase-3. Further, silencing of seladin-1 in this cell line supported involvement of seladin-1 in greater cisplatin responsiveness, which was demonstrated by decreased cell viability and increased expression of apoptotic markers; while its overexpression was associated with a higher survival rate and a clear anti-apoptotic effect. In a first, they showed an important role for seladin-1 in the biology of TGCTs and provided new insights into cisplatin responsiveness of these tumours.

To gain insight into the mechanism of the persistent infection with **hepatitis C virus** (HCV) which induces tumorigenicity in hepatocytes, Nishimura et al. [21] generated monoclonal antibodies on a genome-wide scale against an HCV-expressing human

hepatoblastoma-derived cell line, RzM6-LC, showing augmented tumorigenicity. They identified DHCR24 from this screen and showed that its expression reflected tumorigenicity, as HCV induced the DHCR24 overexpression in human hepatocytes. Their results suggested that DHCR24 is elevated in response to HCV infection and inhibited the p53 stress response by stimulating the accumulation of the MDM2-p53 complex in the cytoplasm and by inhibiting the acetylation of p53 in the nucleus.

Adrenal glands show the highest levels of seladin-1 expression, which are significantly reduced in **adrenal carcinomas** (ACC). Simi et al. [22] investigated whether promoter methylation could account for the down-regulation of seladin-1 expression in ACC. They found that the treatment of cell lines with 5-Aza induced a significant increase of seladin-1 mRNA expression in H295R and SW13. In ACC, methylation density of seladin-1 promoter was higher than in normal adrenal glands, while seladin-1 mRNA expression in ACC was significantly lower than in normal adrenal glands. Thus they concluded that methylation could be involved in the altered pattern of seladin-1 gene expression in ACC.

Lee et al. [23] investigated the functional role of DHCR24 and its clinical relevance in **non-muscle-invasive urothelial carcinoma** (NMIUC) were investigated. They found that the enforced expression of DHCR24 caused proliferation, adhesion, and migration, while DHCR24 loss resulted in slower proliferation and a reduction in cell viabilities compared with control cells. They concluded that DHCR24 was closely associated with progression of NMIUC and showed aggressive properties in human UC cells.

microRNA-124(miR-124) has recently been reported to be elevated in **cardiovascular disease** and Han et al. [24] investigated the exact role of miR-124 in cardiomyocytes and myocardial infarction. Using cultured cardiomyocytes, myocardial-infarction mouse model, and clinical data to study the effects of miR-124 on myocardial ischemia, they found miR-124 up-regulated in H₂O₂ and hypoxia induced cardiomyocyte injury. Further, they identified DHCR24 as a novel functional target of miR-124 in cardiac myocytes. They observed that the miR-124-DHCR24 axis was responsible for cardiomyocyte apoptosis regulation. Furthermore, they found that circulating miR-124 to be elevated in acute myocardial infarction (AMI) patients and correlated with myocardial injury and cardiac function.

Cholesterol is a risk factor for breast cancer and DHCR24 is a key enzyme in the cholesterol synthesis pathway. Qiu et al. [25] found that DHCR24 expression was higher in **breast cancer** especially in luminal and HER2 positive breast cancer tissues compared with normal breast. They found that DHCR24 knockdown reduced whereas DHCR24 overexpression enhanced breast cancer stem-like cell populations such as mammosphere and aldehyde dehydrogenase positive cell numbers. Furthermore, overexpression of DHCR24 increased the expression of the Hedgehog pathway-regulated genes and treating with Hedgehog pathway inhibitor GANT61 blocked DHCR24-induced mammosphere growth and increased mRNA levels of the Hedgehog regulated genes. Also, the expression of a constitutively activated mutant of Smoothened, rescued the decreases in mammosphere growth and Hedgehog regulated gene expression induced by knockdown of DHCR24. Their results pointed that DHCR24 promoted the growth of breast cancer stem-like cells in part through enhancing the Hedgehog signaling pathway.

β -eudesmol is the active compound isolated from *Atractylodes lancea* (Thunb) D.C. The actions of this compound against **cholangiocarcinoma** (CCA) cells include anti-angiogenesis and anti-cell proliferation and growth. To understand the molecular targets of action of β -eudesmol, Kotawong et al. [26] exposed the CCA cells (CL-6) to β -eudesmol for 24 and 48 hours. Their analysis showed that the actions of β -eudesmol were associated with various biological processes particularly apoptosis and cell cycle and one of the possible molecular targets of action of β -eudesmol against CL-6 for cell apoptosis induction DHCR24.

Schrader et al. [27] investigated whether statin therapy (which lower cholesterol and reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease) associated with epigenetics in **Type 2 diabetes** (T2D) patients. They analysed DNA methylation in blood from newly diagnosed T2D patients in All New Diabetics in Scania (ANDIS) and a replication cohort All New Diabetics in Uppsala County (ANDiU) and found that 79 sites were differentially methylated between cases on statins and controls in ANDIS. These included previously statin-associated methylation sites annotated to DHCR24 (cg17901584), ABCG1 (cg27243685) and SC4MOL (cg05119988). Further, differential methylation of two sites related to cholesterol biosynthesis and immune response, cg17901584 (DHCR24) and cg23011663 (ARIH2), were replicated in ANDiU. Thus they concluded that statin therapy associated with epigenetic modifications in T2D patients.

Yuan et al. [28] aimed to characterize the metabolomic profiles regulated by Dipeptidyl Peptidase 4 (DPP4) in methotrexate (MTX)-resistant **gestational trophoblastic neoplastic** (GTN) cells. They observed that cholesterol biosynthesis-related metabolites were markedly impacted by DPP4 knockdown in MTX-resistant sublines and manipulation of DPP4 expression affected the level of cellular cholesterol in GTN cells. Their analysis identified DHCR24 as a potential downstream effector of DPP4. Their findings suggested that DPP4 might regulate DHCR24-mediated cholesterol biosynthesis to promote methotrexate resistance in GTN cells. They hypothesized that targeting DPP4/DHCR24 signaling might help to sensitize MTX-resistant GTN to MTX treatment.

Zhang et al. [29] proposed a functional serine/arginine-rich splicing factor 3 (SRSF3) inhibitor for CRC therapy and elucidated its antitumor mechanisms. They found that silencing SRSF3 markedly inhibited the proliferation and migration of **CRC** cells through suppression of its target gene DHCR24. They observed that the novel SRSF3 inhibitor SFI003 exhibited potent antitumor efficacy in vitro and in vivo, which drove apoptosis of CRC cells via the SRSF3/DHCR24/reactive oxygen species (ROS) axis.

Accumulating evidences reveal that cellular cholesterol deficiency could trigger the onset of **Alzheimer's disease** (AD) and DHCR24 controls cellular cholesterol homeostasis, which has been found to be downregulated in AD vulnerable regions and involved in AD-related pathological activities. Zhang et al. [30] demonstrated the role of DHCR24 in AD by employing delivery of adeno-associated virus carrying DHCR24 gene into the hippocampus of 5xFAD mice. They found the cognitive impairment of 5xFAD mice was significantly reversed after DHCR24-based gene therapy. Furthermore, they revealed that DHCR24 knock-in successfully prevented or reversed AD-related pathology in 5xFAD mice, including amyloid- β deposition, synaptic injuries, autophagy, reactive astrocytosis, microglial phagocytosis and apoptosis. In a first, they demonstrated that the potential value of DHCR24-mediated regulation of

cellular cholesterol level as a promising treatment for AD.

Resistance to cisplatin (DDP) is a significant obstacle that limits the therapeutic efficacy in **Non-small-cell lung cancer** (NSCLC) patients. Qin et al. [31] investigated the role and mechanism of DHCR24 in DDP resistance in NSCLC cells. They found that DHCR24 expression was elevated in DDP-resistant cells, while down-regulation of DHCR24 inhibited the growth of DDP-resistant cells and induced ferroptosis. Further, inhibition of DHCR24 led to the inactivation of the PI3K/AKT/GSK3 β pathway and subsequent induction of ferroptosis. Additionally, it was observed that DHCR24 deficiency improved NSCLC DDP resistance in vivo.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [32] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2nd order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [33] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, •

linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [33].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [34]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [35], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance

based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [32] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [32]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [36], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the

projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. DHCR24 related synergies

Note - DHCR24 was found to be upregulated in Type A. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 307 2nd order combinations of DHCR24 were recorded.

3.1.1. DHCR24 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with DHCR24 showed high rankings - erb-b2 receptor tyrosine kinase 3 (ERBB3), ATP binding cassette subfamily B member 1 (ABCB1), parathyroid hormone like hormone (PTH1LH), PITPNM family member 3 (PITPNM3), annexin A13 (ANXA13), RUN domain containing 3B (RUNDC3B), leucine rich repeat containing 31 (LRRC31), interleukin 1 receptor like 1 (IL1RL1), microtubule affinity regulating kinase 1 (MARK1), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily C member 4 (KCNC4), SSX family member 2 interacting protein (SSX2IP), solute carrier family 16 member 7 (SLC16A7), ATP binding cassette subfamily G member 2 (JR blood group) (ABCG2), periplakin (PPL), polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 12 (GALNT12), cyclin and CBS domain divalent metal cation transport mediator 1 (CNNM1), transmembrane protein 54 (TMEM54), hippocalcin (HPCA), G protein signaling modulator 2 (GPSM2), citron rho-interacting serine/threonine kinase (CIT), nuclear factor, erythroid 2 (NFE2), ATPase phospholipid transporting 8A1 (ATP8A1), ATP binding cassette subfamily C member 4 (PEL blood group) (ABCC4), heat shock protein family A (Hsp70) member 2 (HSPA2), beta-1,4-mannosyl-glycoprotein 4-beta-N-acetylglucosaminyltransferase (MGAT3), LIF interleukin 6 family cytokine (LIF),

filamin C (FLNC), leucine rich repeat containing 4 (LRRC4), coiled-coil domain containing 136 (CCDC136), myosin VC (MYO5C), low density lipoprotein receptor (LDLR), afadin, adherens junction formation factor (AFDN), argininosuccinate synthase 1 (ASS1), EPS8 signaling adaptor L1 (EPS8L1), LARGE xylosyl- and glucuronyltransferase 1 (LARGE1), unc-79 homolog, NALCN channel complex subunit (UNC79), tetratricopeptide repeat domain 9 (TTC9), RAB33A, member RAS oncogene family (RAB33A), proline rich and Gla domain 4 (PRRG4), protein phosphatase 1 regulatory inhibitor subunit 1A (PPP1R1A), KLF transcription factor 4 (KLF4), KIAA0319, p21 (RAC1) activated kinase 6 (PAK6), HECT, C2 and WW domain containing E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 2 (HECW2), HECT and RLD domain containing E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 5 (HERC5), cyclin dependent kinase like 2 (CDKL2), epidermal growth factor (EGF), shisa like 1 (SHISAL1 / KIAA1644), collagen type II alpha 1 chain (COL2A1), SLAIN motif family member 1 (SLAIN1), ring finger protein 157 (RNF157), solute carrier family 47 member 1 (SLC47A1), PR/SET domain 16 (PRDM16), solute carrier family 44 member 3 (SLC44A3), cellular retinoic acid binding protein 2 (CRABP2), thrombospondin type 1 domain containing 7B (THSD7B), atypical chemokine receptor 3 (ACKR3), immunoglobulin superfamily member 11 (IGSF11), coiled-coil domain 39 molecular ruler complex subunit (CCDC39), gamma-aminobutyric acid type A receptor subunit beta2 (GABRB2), serine protease 35 (PRSS35), astrotactin 2 (ASTN2), coiled-coil domain containing 81 (CCDC81), glycoprotein hormone subunit alpha 2 (GPHA2), coiled-coil domain containing 3 (CCDC3), inter-alpha-trypsin inhibitor heavy chain 2 (ITIH2), calcium voltage-gated channel auxiliary subunit alpha2delta 1 (CACNA2D1), serine and arginine rich splicing factor 12 (SRSF12), neural cell adhesion molecule 2 (NCAM2), solute carrier family 26 member 2 (SLC26A2), chloride intracellular channel 2 (CLIC2), glutamate receptor interacting protein 1 (GRIP1), SH3 domain containing ring finger 2 (SH3RF2), STEAP2 metalloredutase (STEAP2), grainyhead like transcription factor 3 (GRHL3), nucleophosmin/nucleoplasmin 2 (NPM2), chloride intracellular channel 6 (CLIC6), actin alpha cardiac muscle 1 (ACTC1), angiotensin I converting enzyme (ACE), spondin 2 (SPON2), cholinergic receptor nicotinic beta 2 subunit (CHRN2), cytochrome P450 family 3 subfamily A member 4 (CYP3A4), NHS like 3 (NHSL3 / KIAA1522), AKNA domain containing 1 (AKNAD1), Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor 3 (ARHGEF3), sphingomyelin synthase 2 (SGMS2), solute carrier family 9 member B2 (SLC9B2), FHF complex subunit HOOK interacting protein 1A (FHIP1A / FAM160A1), ankyrin repeat domain 33B (ANKRD33B), STEAP family member 1 (STEAP1), adenylate cyclase 1 (ADCY1), lysine demethylase 1B (KDM1B), transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily V member 6 (TRPV6), phytanoyl-CoA 2-hydroxylase interacting protein like (PHYHIPL), protein phosphatase 1 regulatory subunit 36 (PPP1R36), calcium voltage-gated channel auxiliary subunit beta 2 (CACNB2), ubiquitin specific peptidase 54 (USP54), serpin family B member 8 (SERPINB8), pleckstrin homology domain containing A7 (PLEKHA7), myosin IA (MYO1A), small G protein signaling modulator 1 (SGSM1), dynein axonemal assembly factor 3 (DNAAF3), neuronal vesicle trafficking associated 1 (NSG1), OTU deubiquitinase 7A (OTUD7A), CDC42 binding protein kinase gamma (CDC42BPG), lysophosphatidic acid receptor 3 (LPAR3), anoctamin 5 (ANO5), cilia and flagella associated protein 46 (CFAP46), angiopoietin like 7 (ANGPTL7), interferon stimulated exonuclease gene 20 (ISG20), membrane bound glycerophospholipid

O-acyltransferase 1 (MBOAT1), tryptase alpha/beta 1 (TPSAB1), bisphosphoglycerate mutase (BPGM), regulator of calcineurin 2 (RCAN2), radial spoke head component 9 (RSPH9), carboxylesterase 4A (CES4A), ciliary microtubule associated protein 3 (CIMAP3 / PIFO), leucine rich repeat and Ig domain containing 2 (LINGO2), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 2A1 (SLCO2A1), family with sequence similarity 91 member A1 (FAM91A1), LRRN4 C-terminal like (LRRN4CL), G protein-coupled receptor 4 (GPR4), endoplasmic reticulum to nucleus signaling 1 (ERN1), WSC domain containing 1 (WSCD1), transmembrane protein 30B (TMEM30B), synemin (SYNM), calpain 12 (CAPN12), coiled-coil serine rich protein 1 (CCSER1), oxysterol binding protein 2 (OSBP2), MAF bZIP transcription factor F (MAFF), RNA binding motif protein 11 (RBM11), transcobalamin 2 (TCN2), limbic system associated membrane protein (LSAMP), insulin induced gene 1 (INSIG1), BCR activator of RhoGEF and GTPase (BCR), natural killer cell cytotoxicity receptor 3 ligand 1 (NCR3LG1), family with sequence similarity 78 member B (FAM78B), FAT atypical cadherin 4 (FAT4), solute carrier family 6 member 9 (SLC6A9), laminin subunit beta 3 (LAMB3), tryptase beta 2 (TPSB2), ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 1 (ENPP1), AFDN divergent transcript (AFDN-DT), SH3 domain binding glutamate rich protein like 2 (SH3BGRL2), ankyrin repeat domain 35 (ANKRD35), sterol regulatory element binding transcription factor 2 (SREBF2) and collagen type XV alpha 1 chain (COL15A1).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of DHCR24 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences -

- Individual members w.r.t DHCR24 with DHCR24 – > ERBB3 / ABCB1 / PTHLH / PITPNM3 / ANXA13 / RUNDC3B / LRRC31 / IL1RL1 / MARK1 / SSX2IP / SLC16A7 / ABCG2 / PPL / GALNT12 / CNNM1 / TMEM54 / HPCA / GPSM2 / CIT / NFE2 / ATP8A1 / ABCC4 / HSPA2 / MGAT3 / LIF / FLNC / LRRC4 / CCDC136 / MYO5C / LDLR / AFDN / ASS1 / EPS8L1 / LARGE1 / UNC79 / TTC9 / RAB33A / PRRG4 / PPP1R1A / KLF4 / KIAA0319 / PAK6 / HECW2 / HERC5 / CDKL2 / EGF / KIAA1644 / COL2A1 / SLAIN1 / RNF157 / SLC47A1 / PRDM16 / SLC44A3 / CRABP2 / THSD7B / ACKR3 / IGSF11 / CCDC39 / GABRB2 / PRSS35 / ASTN2 / CCDC81 / GPHA2 / CCDC3 / ITIH2 / CACNA2D1 / SRSF12 / NCAM2 / SLC26A2 / CLIC2 / GRIP1 / SH3RF2 / STEAP2 / GRHL3 / NPM2 / CLIC6 / ACTC1 / ACE / SPON2 / CHRN2 / CYP3A4 / KIAA1522 / AKNAD1 / ARHGEF3 / SGMS2 / SLC9B2 / FHIP1A / ANKRD33B / STEAP1 / ADCY1 / KDM1B / TRPV6 / PHYHIPL / PPP1R36 / CACNB2 / USP54 / SERPINB8 / PLEKHA7 / MYO1A / SGSM1 / DNAAF3 / NSG1 / OTUD7A / CDC42BPG / LPAR3 / ANO5 / CFAP46 / ANGPTL7 / ISG20 / MBOAT1 / TPSAB1 / BPGM / RCAN2 / RSPH9 / CES4A / CIMAP3 / LINGO2 / SLCO2A1 / FAM91A1 / LRRN4CL / GPR4 / ERN1 / WSCD1 / TMEM30B / SYNM / CAPN12 / CCSER1 / OSBP2 / MAFF / RBM11 / TCN2 / LSAMP / INSIG1 / BCR / NCR3LG1 / FAM78B / FAT4 / SLC6A9 / LAMB3 / TPSB2 / ENPP1 / AFDN-DT / SH3BGRL2 / ANKRD35 / SREBF2 / COL15A1

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS DHCR24									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T DHCR24									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
ERBB3 - DHCR24	196	177	241	38	ABCB1 - DHCR24	287	179	248	18
PTHLH - DHCR24	156	151	217	60	PITPNM3 - DHCR24	166	77	145	302
ANXA13 - DHCR24	140	156	161	235	RUND3B - DHCR24	207	81	159	183
LRRC31 - DHCR24	177	50	163	256	IL1RL1 - DHCR24	283	149	290	9
MARK1 - DHCR24	193	271	232	91	SSX2IP - DHCR24	281	276	281	135
SLC16A7 - DHCR24	178	144	199	250	ABCG2 - DHCR24	221	176	202	130
PPL - DHCR24	165	150	147	296	GALNT12 - DHCR24	298	165	156	159
CNNM1 - DHCR24	86	178	160	294	TMEM54 - DHCR24	203	277	293	76
HPCA - DHCR24	158	193	244	149	GPSM2 - DHCR24	272	304	288	94
CIT - DHCR24	204	188	72	289	NFE2 - DHCR24	152	199	185	224
ATP8A1 - DHCR24	245	282	249	205	ABCC4 - DHCR24	89	182	192	180
HSPA2 - DHCR24	170	280	212	237	MGAT3 - DHCR24	297	274	229	62
LIF - DHCR24	293	305	198	116	FLNC - DHCR24	257	264	296	103
LRRC4 - DHCR24	211	265	259	147	CCDC136 - DHCR24	223	237	203	59
MYO5C - DHCR24	259	241	261	197	LDLR - DHCR24	188	167	226	98
AFDN - DHCR24	255	255	278	78	ASS1 - DHCR24	234	210	271	88
EPS8L1 - DHCR24	292	173	166	278	LARGE1 - DHCR24	264	259	179	139
UNC79 - DHCR24	307	297	216	121	TTC9 - DHCR24	219	220	291	137
RAB33A - DHCR24	276	256	252	97	PRRG4 - DHCR24	205	268	272	73
PPP1R1A - DHCR24	301	300	299	151	KLF4 - DHCR24	227	302	305	77
KIAA0319 - DHCR24	290	287	256	85	PAK6 - DHCR24	289	306	297	67
HECW2 - DHCR24	213	231	125	230	HERC5 - DHCR24	300	180	279	95
CDKL2 - DHCR24	186	91	167	236	EGF - DHCR24	194	120	170	286
KIAA1644 - DHCR24	108	194	235	261	COL2A1 - DHCR24	171	212	103	284
SLAIN1 - DHCR24	270	191	275	102	RNF157 - DHCR24	226	229	227	66
SLC47A1 - DHCR24	286	252	157	141	PRDM16 - DHCR24	176	113	263	164
SLC44A3 - DHCR24	175	262	215	158	CRABP2 - DHCR24	181	207	236	168
THSD7B - DHCR24	183	205	93	292	ACKR3 - DHCR24	157	105	184	282
IGSF11 - DHCR24	153	235	276	93	CCDC39 - DHCR24	265	295	302	170
GABRB2 - DHCR24	191	170	128	210	PRSS35 - DHCR24	295	307	292	63
ASTN2 - DHCR24	149	215	303	174	CCDC81 - DHCR24	148	278	120	242
GPHA2 - DHCR24	163	251	171	119	CCDC3 - DHCR24	299	98	180	263
ITH2 - DHCR24	101	275	228	271	CACNA2D1 - DHCR24	235	248	301	82
SRSF12 - DHCR24	251	139	210	155	NCAM2 - DHCR24	167	238	270	189
SLC26A2 - DHCR24	218	102	186	266	CLIC2 - DHCR24	306	298	295	120
GRIP1 - DHCR24	229	294	219	169	SH3RF2 - DHCR24	162	114	150	145
STEAP2 - DHCR24	144	223	251	240	GRHL3 - DHCR24	169	201	122	295

Table 1: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between DHCR24 VS Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic DHCR24 2^{nd} order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of DHCR24-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS DHCR24									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T DHCR24									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
NPM2 - DHCR24	222	172	193	173	CLIC6 - DHCR24	150	286	121	248
ACTC1 - DHCR24	253	239	158	178	ACE - DHCR24	252	221	289	34
SPON2 - DHCR24	212	184	267	122	CHRN2 - DHCR24	198	100	255	150
CYP3A4 - DHCR24	242	141	205	202	KIAA1522 - DHCR24	285	208	294	92
AKNAD1 - DHCR24	136	186	220	241	ARHGEF3 - DHCR24	232	216	243	126
SGMS2 - DHCR24	230	254	187	100	SLC9B2 - DHCR24	247	197	233	61
FAM160A1 - DHCR24	155	83	152	196	ANKRD33B - DHCR24	266	217	234	132
STEAP1 - DHCR24	187	243	224	177	ADCY1 - DHCR24	261	260	221	101
KDM1B - DHCR24	258	158	142	175	TRPV6 - DHCR24	291	148	195	245
PHYHIPL - DHCR24	215	225	197	182	PPP1R36 - DHCR24	147	291	155	167
CACNB2 - DHCR24	274	293	273	152	USP54 - DHCR24	302	289	246	104
SERPIN8 - DHCR24	267	283	277	83	PLEKHA7 - DHCR24	214	301	207	65
MYO1A - DHCR24	199	258	284	198	SGSM1 - DHCR24	209	234	285	133
DNAAF3 - DHCR24	124	162	280	283	NSG1 - DHCR24	139	263	231	264
OTUD7A - DHCR24	280	246	182	105	CDC42BPG - DHCR24	240	213	282	179
LPAR3 - DHCR24	110	174	162	259	ANO5 - DHCR24	236	187	262	279
CFAP46 - DHCR24	228	169	260	128	ANGPTL7 - DHCR24	268	226	173	222
ISG20 - DHCR24	278	279	213	172	MBOAT1 - DHCR24	210	189	56	216
TPSAB1 - DHCR24	159	136	182	280	BPGM - DHCR24	277	240	298	80
RCAN2 - DHCR24	249	303	264	143	RSPH9 - DHCR24	206	143	223	163
CES4A - DHCR24	271	244	247	176	PIFO - DHCR24	201	267	237	131
LINGO2 - DHCR24	109	190	176	307	SLCO2A1 - DHCR24	241	181	85	223
FAM91A1 - DHCR24	305	206	222	117	LRRN4CL - DHCR24	282	266	257	154
GPR4 - DHCR24	256	273	274	161	ERN1 - DHCR24	279	292	283	56
WSCD1 - DHCR24	273	233	306	109	TMEM30B - DHCR24	224	218	165	243
SYNM - DHCR24	200	214	137	265	CAPN12 - DHCR24	164	245	265	191
CCSER1 - DHCR24	185	142	153	226	OSBP2 - DHCR24	98	198	146	303
MAFF - DHCR24	123	236	239	249	RBM11 - DHCR24	179	111	238	185
TCN2 - DHCR24	237	230	194	107	LSAMP - DHCR24	195	103	148	193
INSIG1 - DHCR24	246	249	307	148	BCR - DHCR24	288	285	174	146
NCR3LG1 - DHCR24	303	242	242	108	FAM78B - DHCR24	172	195	268	112
FAT4 - DHCR24	220	247	225	244	SLC6A9 - DHCR24	145	171	254	165
LAMB3 - DHCR24	202	269	169	186	TPSB2 - DHCR24	154	261	69	234
ENPP1 - DHCR24	248	228	190	268	AFDN-DT - DHCR24	189	250	269	64
SH3BGRL2 - DHCR24	239	128	177	188	ANKRD35 - DHCR24	233	290	214	113
SREBF2 - DHCR24	254	257	201	184	COL15A1 - DHCR24	304	202	287	124

Table 2: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between DHCR24 VS Individual members.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t DHCR24

ERBB3 / ABCB1 / PTHLH / PITPNM3 / ANXA13 ...	
RUNDC3B / LRRC31 / IL1RL1 / MARK1 / ...	
SSX2IP / SLC16A7 / ABCG2 / PPL / GALNT12 ...	
CNNM1 / TMEM54 / HPCA / GPSM2 / CIT / NFE2 ...	
ATP8A1 / ABCC4 / HSPA2 / MGAT3 / LIF / FLNC ...	
LRRC4 / CCDC136 / MYO5C / LDLR / AFDN / ASS1 ...	
EPS8L1 / LARGE1 / UNC79 / TTC9 / RAB33A ...	
PRRG4 / PPP1R1A / KLF4 / KIAA0319 / PAK6 ...	
HECW2 / HERC5 / CDKL2 / EGF / KIAA1644 ...	
COL2A1 / SLAIN1 / RNF157 / SLC47A1 / PRDM16 ...	
SLC44A3 / CRABP2 / THSD7B / ACKR3 / IGSF11 ...	
CCDC39 / GABRB2 / PRSS35 / ASTN2 / CCDC81 ...	
GPHA2 / CCDC3 / ITIH2 / CACNA2D1 / SRSF12 ...	
NCAM2 / SLC26A2 / CLIC2 / GRIP1 / SH3RF2 ...	
STEAP2 / GRHL3 / NPM2 / CLIC6 / ACTC1 / ACE ...	
SPON2 / CHRNB2 / CYP3A4 / KIAA1522 / AKNAD1 ...	
ARHGEF3 / SGMS2 / SLC9B2 / FHIP1A / ANKRD33B ...	
STEAP1 / ADCY1 / KDM1B / TRPV6 / PHYHIPL ...	
PPP1R36 / CACNB2 / USP54 / SERPINB8 ...	
PLEKHA7 / MYO1A / SGSM1 / DNAAF3 / NSG1 ...	
OTUD7A / CDC42BPG / LPAR3 / ANO5 / CFAP46 ...	
ANGPTL7 / ISG20 / MBOAT1 / TPSAB1 / BPGM ...	
RCAN2 / RSPH9 / CES4A / CIMAP3 / LINGO2 ...	
SLCO2A1 / FAM91A1 / LRRN4CL / GPR4 / ERN1 ...	
WSCD1 / TMEM30B / SYNM / CAPN12 / CCSER1 ...	
OSBP2 / MAFF / RBM11 / TCN2 / LSAMP / INSIG1 ...	
BCR / NCR3LG1 / FAM78B / FAT4 / SLC6A9 ...	
LAMB3 / TPSB2 / ENPP1 / AFDN-DT / SH3BGRL2 ...	
ANKRD35 / SREBF2 / COL15A1	DHCR24

Table 3: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between DHCR24 and Individual members.

Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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